

SOCIO-CULTURAL PRACTICES IN THE FILLING UP OF NIKAHNAMA AND ITS EFFECTS ON WOMEN'S MARITAL RIGHTS IN LAHORE

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ABSTRACT

Background: The aim of the research study was to find out the social and cultural practices that were prevalent in filling up the important clauses of the nikahnama (13 to 21). Marriage is a legal agreement between the bride and groom, how much the bride was involved in this legal contract, how socio-cultural practices affected women's marital rights and become the cause of divorce.

Methodology: Multiple stage samples were used to select the respondents. Respondents were selected through purposive sampling techniques. The sample size was consisted of 30 divorced women from Lahore district. In-depth interviews were conducted with the help of interview guide to gather information from the respondents.

Result The conclusion of this study that marital rights of women were affected by social and cultural practices which could be mentioned in the prescribed column of nikahnama. The study's analysis is that social and cultural practices are an obstacle to protecting women's marital rights and filling up of those important clauses that protect women from divorce. The rate of unilateral divorce is also increasing due to incomplete fill up important clauses of the nikahnama.

INTRODUCTION

Nikahnama is a legal, civil and written contract between the man and woman. The marriage contract, in its most basic form, reflects the couple's willingness to marry without pressure and is signed in the presence of competent witnesses. The agreement allows couples to discuss important aspects of their marriage and make binding agreements before becoming husband and wife. Islamic marriage agreements are very practical tools that allow couples to engage in negotiations

to ensure that their larger goals and philosophies are compatible (Mohammad & Lehmann 2011). Child Marriage Restraint Act 1929, the minimum legal age of marriage is 16 years for girls and 18 years for boys. One party must be male and one female, the mental capacity of the both parties must be of sound mind (Khan & Khan 2019). Nikahnama legal document has 25 clauses, 1 to 12 clauses are based on the basic information and 13 to 21 clauses in which the

Muslim couples can write down the term and conditions / rights and obligations according to their own will. These clauses are bound the couples to fulfill their own rights and obligation / terms and conditions that will be applicable in their married life. Signature/thumb mark on this legal contract is done between the Muslim male and female in the presence of witnesses and Nikah Registrar. Both side bride and groom consent and signatures are necessary on this legal contract, if one deny there will be no contract. The under Sharia law, verbal nikah is as good as it is written. However, under state law, a Nikahnama must be signed and registered. It is always best to have each agreement in writing to serve as better evidence in court (Jawad 2019).

History of Basic Muslim Family Law ordinance

Family law describes to legal matters relating to marriage, divorce, legal separation, child custody and support, alimony (spousal support), adoption and related issues and no doubt that Islam has provided a solid, clear and effective family law. Every Part of this system seek for sustainability, success and Well being of mankind which not only the source of an effective and productive family but also for conducive and prosperous society. Pakistan is an Islamic ideological state which is based on the foundations of two-nation theory, and main motive of its formation is to exercise the Islamic laws in an independent state. After the creation of Pakistan for Implant of these objectives a constitution of Islamic Republic of Pakistan had drafted in the light of shariah (Islamic law). The Muslim Family Law Ordinance was first constituted on 17 February 1965 to consider consultation in this meeting chaired by Allaudin Siddiqui. In terms of legislating Islam, the Muslim Family Law Ordinance 1961 made recommendations for appropriate amendments in the light of the Qur'an and Sunnah. The counsel completed his three times readings by March 1967 and final recommendations were made at the Council meeting on March 28, 1967 in Lahore (Noor & Mehfooz 2019).

Socio –Cultural Practices

Social practices are those social ways that are (mostly) performed more commonly and habitually in society. It meant for people to be part of their daily life activities. These activities are performed as usual and combine different types of elements, such as physical and mental activities, material artifacts, knowledge, emotions, and skills and so on (Reckwitz 2002). It is very important to understand that the religion of Islam and people's cultural traditions are two different things. Many Muslims are extremely influenced by their individual cultural backgrounds. Islam is an especially culturally diverse religion (Mohammad &Lehmann 2011).

Rights and Obligations / Terms and Conditions in Nikahnama Clauses

The Form of Nikahnama as prescribed by rules 8 and 10 of the Rules under the Muslim family Law ordinance 1961. In nikahnama 1 to 12 clauses are consist on the information like name of the bride and groom , age, date of birth, CNIC, residence address, status of bride, witnesses of the both side. 13 to 16 clauses are based on the Haq Mahr.

Clauses #13, 14, 15, 16

There are two types of Haq Mahr, muajal also called prompt and ghair Muajal called deferred. Muajal must be paid on the nikah time and ghair Muajal will be paid after the demand of the bride. Mahr is the gift of cash or wealth given to the bride by her husband at the time of her marriage. The Mahr is the sole right and personal property of the bride. It also means that she has the right to decide on money and payment methods, and this is where most of our society fails to ensure women's rights (Aiman 2018).

while he has already wife. According to the Muslim Family Law Ordinance (MFLO), he needs the permission of the Union Council to marry someone else. The union council investigates and seeks permission from the current wife to allow a second marriage (Naveed 2016).

Unilateral Divorce

Unilateral divorce means that one spouse decides to end the marriage without the other's consent. The unilateral divorce is process by one partner without consulting or informing the other partner, be it husband or wife. The main purpose of this divorce is to harm and insult both parties, both psychologically and emotionally. Such divorces are mainly committed by strangers against their wives. Although, comprehensive statistics on divorce are not available across the country, according to media sources, in Rawalpindi alone, for one month of September 2019, the family court issued 11 notices of khula, while in 74 cases husbands had filed for divorce. Filed a petition for these figures are different from the above notion that the real claimants to divorce are still husbands, who in many cases are "one-sided" by nature (Awan 2020).

Objectives

- To explore those Socio- cultural practices in the filling up all clauses of Nikahnama.
- To identify those marital rights which may affected by the socio cultural practices when fill up the Nikahnama clauses.
- To identify that incomplete Nikahnama can a cause of divorce

Research Questions

1. What are socio- cultural practices in the filling up of Nikahnama?
2. What kind of marital rights which may affected due to the socio-cultural practices?
3. Is Incomplete Nikahnama clauses (13 to 21) can be cause of unilateral divorce?

Methodology

Research approach that was used for this research that is qualitative and research design is

descriptive. The divorced women were the targeted population of district Lahore. The researcher did get the divorced women list from union councils of District Lahore. Lahore district population is higher (11.12 million) as compare to the Faisalabad (3.20) million and Rawalpindi (2.09) million. Lahore district is selected because of its population density (per person per kilometer) (Population Survey 2017).Lahore district density is higher (6278.30) as compare to the Faisalabad (1334.50) and Rawalpindi (1022.70) (Punjab Bureau of statistics 2019-2020).

Multiple stage sampling was used for the selection of the respondents.

- At 1st stage Punjab province was selected due to the high divorce rate as compare to the other provinces. Punjab Bureau statistics demonstrate that Punjab divorce rate is high 0.45 as compare to the other provinces, sindh 0.23.KPK 0.15, Balochistan 0.14.
- At 2nd stage there were high divorce rate districts shortlisted; there have been 10,766 divorces in Lahore, 16,305 in Faisalabad and 11,707 in Rawalpindi in a year. Socio –Economic Profile by District Punjab (2019-2020).
- At 3rd stage Lahore district was selected randomly out of 3 districts.
- At 4th stage 2 towns were selected randomly out of nine towns.
- At 5th stage 3 union councils have been selected randomly out of 274 union councils.
- At 6th stage the respondents were selected by purposive sampling technique from the selected union councils.

The sample size was consisted of 30 divorced females at district Lahore. The in- depth interviews were conducted to get information with the help of interview guide.

Result and Discussion

Social practices in the filling up of Nikahnama Role of Bride in nikahnama discussion

Most of the divorced women were not involved in the discussion over their own nikahnama. One respondent has admitted that just one day before of the wedding, she requested to her father that

she wanted to see her nikahnama. She looked but did not understand the clauses. As a similar study that in Pakistan married couples sign their marriage certificates without reading the nikahnama (Sarwari 2020).

Role of Parents

It was analyzed from the discussion that due to the shyness of their parents they did not any kind of discussion about the nikahnama clauses before of the wedding day or at nikah time. As similar study concluded that unfortunately, it is so embarrassing to admit that we, the literate society, also pay more attention to wedding not marriage. Discuss the Nikahnama has now become a taboo subject in our culture. It is unfair for not only our Maulvi Sahib but also the bride's own family to object to our voices on the terms written in the contract in the celebration of happiness. They allowed us to silent in front of everyone because in our culture it is considered against the modesty and family reputation to speak out for the rights of women who have been cancelled or left blank of a contract before the bride signature (Sab 2019).

Role of Nikah Registrar

Most of the divorced women answered that at the nikah time nikah registrar only used the words Haq Mehr and Qabol hai, but did not explain the clauses, one respondent replied that nikah registrar only asked me the condition but did not explain that how many types of conditions and what kind of statements that could be mentioned in the prescribed columns. Another similar study described that there are clauses that you may not be aware of that, the Maulvi have been tempted to cross because he considered them irrelevant or contrary to tradition (Haq 2012). Another similar study described that Imams / Maulvis / Khatibs / Registrars modified the official Nikahnama without the consent of the married couple, and important provisions protecting the wife are selected without informing the couple. Add to this the fact that most of these marriages are not read in such detail and in the absence of complete information, brides generally do not even know what is missing (Zubari 2007).

Role of the other Source of Information

It was examined that there was no source of information about the nikahnama clauses, one respondent told that her marriage time one commercial was shown on TV about the clauses but soon the advisement was not shown on regular bases. Most of the participant admitted that they did not have knowledge regarding nikahnama clauses, similar findings done by (Arjumand, Malik & Javed, 2021).

Role of Bride's wakeel / gahwah

It was analyzed from the findings that there was no guidance and role of the gahwah /wakeel. As a similar study described that in practice the brides as well as their families, do not understand the terms of the agreement they are signing (Vyborny, Field & Zahir 2019).

Cultural Practices in the filling up of Nikahnama

Family Education

It was observed from the result that mostly belonged to educated families; very few respondents were belonged to illiterate background. Due to the prevalence of ignorant and oppressive cultural practices in Pakistan, the girls' families are worried about how husbands and in-laws will treat their daughters after marriage (Saeed 2019).

Involvement of the Elders / Biradri

It was concluded from the findings that their elders of Biradri had decided the marriage and nikahnama related decision, few respondents had an own choice marriage therefore they were involved in wedding programs but were not involved in nikahnama filling up. Few respondents had a nuclear family therefore the sisters and brother –in laws and her brothers were involved in the fill up of nikahnama. As a similar study mentioned that families and nikah khawan do not allow the bride and groom to reconsider their marriage contract, which is based on their relationship. Mostly the elders removed the most important and sensitive clauses of the marriage contract without the consent of the bride. However, if a bride tries to express her opinion on

a marriage contract, the families on both sides silence her (Ali 2019).

Family/ Biradri/ Caste traditions in Nikahnama

It was analyzed from the observation that they were mostly focused on Haq Mahr + gold +property. Most of the respondents replied that marriages were in their own caste and in relatives so did not emphasis the huge amount of Haq Mahr+ gold +property. Less than half of the respondents said that their marriages were own choice so there was not written any kind of property in nikahnama but orally was promised. A Mehr is a gift that a husband gives to his wife at their wedding. It can be in the form of anything - property, jewelry or cash. According to Islam, when it comes to deciding the Mehr, no burden should be placed on the groom and it should be paid at the time of marriage. However, our society has changed this perception - the Mehr is usually given to the wife after divorce. There are two stages to paying the Haq Mehr: (1) Muajal: Give immediately (2) ghair Muajal: Give in later stages. All these important details need to be addressed beforehand (Naveed 2016).

Involvement of ex -In - laws and husband

Mostly respondents said yes there was too much involvement of the ex – in -laws and husbands. Almost all clauses have been filled by their choice. There are widespread reports that the marriage contract has been amended and deliberately removed to please the boy's family (Dawn 2011).

Attitude of both parties

It was concluded from the findings that mostly faced aggressive attitude when filling up especially Haq Mahr clauses.

Marital Rights

Clauses link marital rights

It was analyzed from the result that mostly did not know the link between the clauses and marital rights .Only Haq Mahr muajal clause was filled. Very few replied that gold was mentioned in the Column of ghair muajal Haq Mahr. In the Similar study mentioned that written contract sets out the terms of the agreement - after the fact, otherwise limits the ability of either party to claim anything.

Covenant law recognizes the superiority of written versus oral contracts through a provision known as the “four corners Doctrine”. The rule states that if there is a conflict between the written agreement and any of the verbal terms used by the parties, the words have been written in the four corners document page that will be considered authentic and govern with the agreement(White 2020). Under the agreement, the couple is allowed to discuss important aspects of their marriage and make a binding agreement before becoming a husband and wife. For example, contracts may include career and child-related living or residency decisions (Mohammad & Lehmann 2011).

Kind of statements in clauses

There was minimum amount of Money only in the Haq Mahr muajal Colum. Very few respondents replied gold was written in ghair muajal clause. Most of the respondents replied that Cut / Crossed line in 17 to 21 clauses, only two respondents replied that minimum pocket money was mentioned in the column but don't know in which Colum. As a similar study described that in prenuptial contract conditions the bride and groom can offer the terms of the agreement, and if it is agreed upon, the marriage becomes a legally binding condition. Most of the terms include agreements about the country where the couple will live, the wife's right to continue her education or career, or arrangements to meet the in-laws. Any condition permitted in Islamic law may be part of the marriage contract, provided both parties agree (Huda 2018).Most of us have observed that some parts of Nikahnama have been crossed (Khalid 2017).

Reasons behind to cut the clauses

It was figure out from the observation that due to superstitious, lack of proper legal guidance, social cultural influence and pressure of the in-laws and relatives were the causes to cut the clauses. Mostly replied almost the same practices were applied in their siblings and other's family wedding, that's why the same procedure was applied at their time of marriage. Mostly said that one of the major cause to cut the clauses that is superstitious because on the time of nikah the

word divorce in any kind of sense considered unfortunate and any type of demand does considered greediness, not proper guidance from any sides that's why to cut the clauses especially 17 to 21. As a similar study In Peshawar, a city in the northwest, about three-quarters of women, most of them illiterate, said they have not been consulted on marriage contracts. If women do so they will be accused of bad manners or causing disaster (because it is unfortunate to talk about divorce before marriage begins). In some cases, marriage registrars, who are usually imams, take matters into their own hands, overcoming bridal-friendly clauses on contracts (Sarwari 2020).

Bride concern about marital rights

The results showed that they exactly did not know how and what type of statement could be mentioned in the clauses and obviously they felt shy and hesitation that if they have discussed the Nikahnama clauses and asked about rights at the nikah time it will be bad for future life and the wedding programs will be destroyed. Often the parts of nikahnama that protect a girl's rights and privileges are removed with contempt. Even a highly educated bride is kept in the dark and forced to sign the document. Illegal and irrelevant entries in this important document have more affected to women than men (Dawn 2011).

Affected Marital Rights

Kinds of affected marital rights

It was analyzed that most of the problems did they face those were domestic violence, 2nd marriage of the husband, drug abuser and no proper income of husband, no choice of separate accommodation, clashes with in-laws. No choice of job and education. Most of the respondents replied that all kind of marital rights have been affected in married life. One stated that her husband had snatched her salary, beaten and abused her physically and psychologically. As a similar study concluded that In Pakistani society, the family as a unit of social and cultural systems is a basic institution of socialization and child rearing. However, with the increasing rate of divorce in Pakistani families over the past few decades, the psychosocial well-being of women and children has been severely affected. Divorce

and post-divorce adjustment are major issues for women in Pakistani social and cultural context. The effects of divorce on women's lives include social stigma, psychological distress, and economic crisis and remarriage issues (Qamar & Faizan 2021).

Responsibility to fill the clauses

It was concluded from the discussion that mostly claimed that firstly nikah registrar is responsible 2nd parents and third self responsible. As a similar study mentioned that most women are not aware of their rights and how to fill out the document. At the same time, the nikah registrars who are responsible for filling out the document themselves do not understand it correctly and often eliminate an incomplete and incorrect one. This incomplete document has ultimately affected on women marital rights. As government officials, nikah registrars have a duty to ensure that women are informed of their basic rights (Dawn 2018).

Unilateral Divorce

Reason of divorce

It was analyzed that all respondents replied that clause #18 and #19 have been cut/crossed, half of the respondents replied that domestic violence was the reason of the divorce. One replied with pain that her height was short that's why he divorced her. Three respondents replied 2nd marriage was the reason of the divorced. One respondent replied that her husband divorced after 25 years of marriage because of the 2nd marriage. One respondent said that her husband and in-laws threatened to divorce her if she did not take property from her family. Three of the respondents replied that they have been taken khula because there was too much toxic relationship with their husband and in-laws. One of the respondent replied that her husband was not a good man doing illegal unethical work that's why she has been taken khula. One respondent replied that she was divorced because of the daughter's birth, her in-laws and husband wanted the son that's why he divorced her. One respondent said he divorced her because she has no baby.

As a similar study mentioned that the reasons for divorced which are common in Pakistan that

alcohol addiction, financial problem, physical and emotional abuse, personal difference, interference of parents and in-laws, lack of maturity, lack of patience, watta satta, religious conversation, culture and lifestyle differences. Lack of trust is the reason of high divorce rate (Gul, Arab & Bloch, 2018).

The Muslim Family Law Ordinance 1961 is more flexible in favor of women than in other Muslim countries on the basis of protection against the limited polygamy and the unilateral right of men to divorce. In fact, family law, especially divorce law, still fails to generalize. Divorce mentioned in the 18th column of the marriage form is a right of delegate which protects the rights of women; if it is taken advantage of then the right of divorce can be assigned to the wife. The terms of a marital agreement can guarantee a woman many of her Islamic rights, which can be enforced by law (Maqsood, Sarwer, Anwer & Rehman, 2018). The main reasons for divorce are economic, marital violence and jealousy. Poverty and unemployment are the main factors that lead a couple to divorce (Mucjaj & Xeka 2015).

Consent

It was analyzed from the findings that most of the divorced have not been by mutual consent, more than half of the respondents said that they had not been wanted to divorce because they have children. Most of the respondents unaware of the arbitration procedure by the union councils even they were not received notices by the union councils. Most of the respondents wanted to reconcile but in response disrespectful behaviour from the husband and in-laws. Most of the respondents accept the divorce by forcefully because they think there have no law in Pakistan to stop the divorce from the women side. Marriage contract is like any other civil contract, the parties can enter any terms and conditions in it, and the bride has the right to exercise the right of divorce 'with condition' or 'without any condition'. This means that if a woman wants to clearly retain this right, it is necessary to mention it clearly when fulfilling this clause in the marriage form. Just as a woman's right to divorce her husband can be determined in a marriage form, so a husband's right to divorce his wife can be curtail

in the same way. For example, a wife may place conditions on her husband's right to divorce. She can stipulate financial compensation if her husband divorces her after the children and she can also take restriction on the 2nd marriage without taking her permission (Shaheen 2021).

As a similar study described that divorce, domestic disputes have increased in Karachi and 14,943 cases have been filed in the city court. Last year, more than 2,000 women divorced their husbands, and more than 2,100 children lost the love and affection of their parents. According to the court records, 14,943 cases were registered in the city court during the last one and a half years while 4,752 such cases were disposed of in the last 1 and a half years. In 2019 almost 11,143 cases were registered in the 4 districts of the city court, while 3,800 such cases were registered in the first three months of that year (Khan 2020). In Lahore city more than 100 divorces were registered in family courts in a day. The divorce rate is increasing not only in the upper class but also in lower and middle classes. From February 2005 to January 2008 almost 75,000 divorce cases had been registered. Approximately 1,24141 divorce cases were registered from February 2008 to May 2011. Over the last decade around (2,59064) separations had been taken place in the Lahore city. In 2010, 40,410 divorce cases were filed in the city's family courts and 13,500 divorced had been taken place in 2011 (Rao 2011).

Suggestions

It suggested that if women don't want divorce how they can protect the divorce in nikahnama. Before the time of the nikah there should be proper guidance of the bride and groom and their parents by the lawyers and nikah registrar. This is the time of social media; the information should be collected from the authentic way. People should be known their rights and obligation in the nikahnama before the marriage. Lawyer must be appointed at the time of nikah because he knows the legalities of the nikahnama clauses. Most of the respondents were facing lots of financial, social and psychological problems after divorce. Most of the women said with pain that their relatives and family members mocked and taunted

her divorce; they did not get the divorce by their own choice. They leave the social activity because of the negative remarks. It has been suggested that there must be medical checkup (physical and psychological) of bride and groom before the nikkah and authentic report must be attached with the nikahnama. It suggested that family should be united because the children faced lots of psychological, social and economic problems, without father their socialization is very difficult for single mothers. Most of the respondents said that there has no guaranty of the marriage how long it will be. For the dignity of the women the law makers and ulma-e-aikaram should be consensus and guide the women that how she can save her marriage in nikahnama.

As a similar study described that the structure of society in Pakistan encourages women to play their role to take care of their family, and their activities are limited to the home. As a result, ending a spouse's financial support in the event of a marriage breakdown makes women from all walks of life extremely vulnerable. This is one of the main reasons why women are living a life of abuse despite their long neglect and suffering. Lack of state support for single women exacerbates vulnerabilities. There is no provision for government housing or unemployment benefits for economically dependent women in Pakistan (Viqar 2020). Divorce is one of the biggest problems that facing society today. Divorce can be considered a social wound, as it can also be a great emotional shock to adults and children. In most cases, divorce is due to social problems such as: unpleasant marriages, sexual violence, psychological violence, crime, etc. Divorce is a legal issue as well as a social and primarily because when there is a no feeling, intimacy, communication and no doubt that the relationship no longer works between the two partners. Divorce is a very stressful situation for all members of the family who experience it and are presented as a major change in an individual's life, which takes a long time to recover and adjust in normal life (Mucaj & Xeka 2015).

REFERENCES

- Awan ,Z.(2020).The Other Side of Divorce. Retrieved from <https://nation.com.pk/03-Mar-2020/the-other-side-of-divorce>
- Aiman, S. (2018). The Mehr mystery. Retrieved from <https://www.the-daily-star.net/lifestyle/special-feature/news/the-mehr-mystery-1668853>
- Ali, N. (2019). Ladies you can divorce your husbands. Retrieved from <https://dailytimes.com.pk/471235/it-is-a-morning-and-afternoon-story-about-right-to-divorce-delegated-to-women/>
- Arjumand, M., Malik, S., &Javed, N. (2021). Knowledge and Awareness about Nikah Nama Reforms and its Clauses in Lahore .*Forman Journal of Social Sciences* , 1
DOI:10.32368/FJSS.20210107 1
- Bilal, M. (2017). Deconstructing the Nikkah Form from a feminist perspective within the Pakistani context. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/36464123/Deconstructing_the_Nikkah_form_from_a_feminist-Perspective_within_the_Pakistani_Context
- Dawn. (2011).Women's right &nikahnama. Retrieved from <https://www.dawn.com/news/621003/womens-rights-nikahnam>
- Dawn. (2018).Nikahnama impact on legal rights of Women .Retrieved from <https://www.dawn.com/news/1445901>
- Gul, A., Arab, N., & Baloch, M,A. (2018). High Ratio of Divorce and its Rationale in Pakistan Publisher: *International Society of Applied Preventive Medicine i-gap*, 9(2), 24-32. DOI10.22359/cswhi_9_2_04 ©2018
- Ghazali, A, S. (1999). Islamic Pakistan Illusion &Reality: National Book Club. Retrieved from http://ghazali.net/book1/chapter_4.htm
- Haq, M. (2012). .what you need to know about the Nikahnama. Retrieved from <https://tribune.com.pk/story/404557/what-you-need-to-know-about-the-nikahnama>

- Huda. (2018). The Legal Marriage Contract in Islam. Retrieved from <https://www.learningreligious.com/theIslamic-marriage-contract-2004429>
- Jawad, A. (2019).Nikkah and importance of Nikahnama. Retrieved from <https://binishnauman.com/2019/12/15/nikkah-and-importance-of-nikkah-nama/>
- Khan, A. (2020).Divorce, Family dispute cases surge in Karachi. Retrieved from <https://www.bolnews.com/pakistan/2020/06/divorce-dispute-cases-surge-in-karachi>
- Khan, H, H., &Khan, A. (2019). Women’s Rights and the Nikah Nama in Pakistan. Retrieved from https://www.cerp.org.pk/updata/files/files/41_20200504004625.pdf
- Khalid, L. (2017). Before Saying Ido.Retrieved from <https://www.thenews.com.pk/magazine/you/2265577-Before-saying-I-do>
- Khurram, M. (2019).*The Basic Muslim Family Laws* (5th ed) Lahore: Muneeb Book House
- Mahmood, M.(2008).*Mahmood, D, F.Mulla’s Principle of Islamic Law* (8th ed) Lahore: Al Qanoon Publisher.
- Malik, M. (2016).You should know your nikahnama before signing it .Retrieved from <https://tribune.com.pk/author/10881/maryammalik>
- Mengal, M. (2019).Know Your Rights (A guide into Nikahnama).Retrieved from <https://fempowermovement.com/know-your-rights-a-guide-into-nikkah-nama/>
- Manzoor, M. (2017).A Women friendly nikahnama and women’s right to divorce. Retrieved from <https://feminisminindia.com/2017/04/27/nikkah-nama-muslim-women-divorce/>
- Mohammad ,I,J.,& Lehmann,C.(2011). Women’s Rights in Islam Regarding Marriage and Divorce. Retrieved from <https://open.mitchellamline.edu/lawandpractice/vol4/iss1/3>
- Mucaj, A., &Xeka, S. (2015).Divorce and Psycho-Social Effects on Adolescents in Albania. *European Scientific Journal, ESJ, 11*(14). Retrieved from <https://ejournal.org/index.php/esj/article/view/5695>
- Naveed, S. (2016). 5 Important Things You Should Check Before Signing Your Nikahnama. Retrieved from <https://www.parhlo.com/the-importance-of-understanding-nikkah-nammah-clauses/>
- Naqvi,L,J.(2018).There is more to the nikahnama than the dotted line. Retrieved from <https://www.thenews.com.pk/magazine/you/409362-there-is-more-to-the-nikkahnama-than-the-dotted-line>
- Nishtar, L. (2018).women’s right under family law. Retrieved from <https://tribune.com.pk/story/1757432/womens-rights-family-law>
- Noor, R.,& Mehfooz, M. (2019). *Prolific Contribution of Council of Islamic Ideology for Islamization of Muslim Family Law Ordinance 1961: An Overview. Quarterly Research Journal of Faculty of Shariah & Law, 3* (3&4). Retrieved from <https://www.iiu.edu.pk/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/2-CII-role.pdf>
- Population, S. (2017).Population, Labor Force and Employment. Retrieved from <https://www.finance.gov.pk/survey/chapters18/12-population.pdf>
- Qamar,A,H.,&Faizan,H,F. (2021).Reasons, Impact, and Post-divorce Adjustment: Lived Experience of Divorced Women in Pakistan, *Journal of Divorce & Remarriage, 62*(5), 349-373, DOI: [10.1080/10502556.2021.1871840](https://doi.org/10.1080/10502556.2021.1871840)
- Ramzan, S ., Akhtar,S ., Ahmad ,S., Zafar , M, U., &Yousaf ,H.(2018). Divorce Status and Its Major Reasons in Pakistan. *Sociology and Anthropology, 6*(4), 386 - 391. DOI: [10.13189/sa.2018.060405](https://doi.org/10.13189/sa.2018.060405).
- Reckwitz,A. (2002). Toward a Theory of Social Practices. *European Journal of Sociology, 5*(2), 243–263.<http://jasss.soc.surrey.ac.uk/17/1/17.html#reckwitz2002>

- Rao, I. (2011). Divorce rate climb .Retrieved from <https://archive.pakistantoday.com.pk/2011/06/26/divorce-rate-climb>
- Sab's Lounge.(2019).Nikah Nama: The most important contract goes unnoticed! Why? Retrieved from <https://sabslounge.medium.com/nikah-nama-the-most-important-contract-goes-unnoticed-why-beb32d13c7d8>
- Saeed, S. (2019).A Girl Should Know These Things before Signing on Nikahnama. Retrieved from <https://www.daytimes.pk/a-girl-should-know-these-things-before-signing-on-nikah-nama-20690/amp/>
- Shaheen, F. (2021).Know Your Rights: Signing Nikah-Nama without Understanding It May Result in Regret. Retrieved from <https://nayadur.tv/2021/07/know-your-rights-signing-nikah-nama-without-understanding-it-may-result-in-regret/>
- Sarwari, A. (2020).Clawless Clauses how Pakistani brides inadvertently sign away their rights. Retrieved from <https://www.economist.com/asia/2020/02/20/how-pakistani-brides->
- Statistics, B. (2019-2020). Socio- Economic Profile by District Punjab. Retrieved from <file:///C:/Users/H%20T%20computer/Downloads/Districts%20socio%20economic%20profile%20-Updated.pdf>
- Tiwari, G. (2017).What is Social Exchange Theory and Explanation .Retrieved from <https://www.sociologygroup.com/social-exchange-theory>
- Viqar, F. (2020). Thematic Report on the Issue of Financial Protection upon Divorce: Muslim Women's Rights under Family Laws in Pakistan- Article 16.Retrieved from https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/Treaties/CEDAW/Shared%20Documents/PAK/INT_CEDAW_CSS_PAK_40942_E.docx
- Vyorny,K.,Field.,&Zahir,H.(2019).Informed consent is needed in Pakistan's marriage contract. Retrieved from <https://www.opml.co.uk/blog/informed-consent-is-needed-in-pakistan-s-marriage-contracts>
- Warraich, Y, A. (2021).Divorce and disparity. Retrieved from <https://www.dawn.com/news/1613356/divorce-and-disparity>
- Maqsood,A.,Safder,S.,Anwer,M.,&Rehman,G.(2018).An Exploratory Study of Perception An Exploratory Study of Perceptions about the Delegated Right of Divorce for Women (Talaq-i-Tafwid) in Pakistan .*FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, 12(1), 227-236
- White, J. (2020) .Why a written contract is better than a verbal agreement. Retrieved from <https://kirasystems.com/learn/why-a-written-contract-is-better-than-a-verbal-agreement/>
- Zubari, B. (2007). Missing Paragraphs in the Nikahnama? Retrieved from <https://medium.com/bz-notes/missing-paragraphs-in-the-nikah-nama-ea708477bec9>.